

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

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ABSTRACT: Lack of studies linking student support services and financial assistance, particularly the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) undergraduate scholarship, to college outcomes such as persistence has been one of the issues in STEM education in the Philippines. Even though previous findings have shown the clear impact of financial support on student success, local researchers have only focused on student satisfaction with the Tertiary Education Subsidy (TES) and persistence. This is why the researchers decided to determine the relationship between the satisfaction of scholarship services provided by the DOST in terms of scholarship updates, support for scholars' organizations and activities, staff assistance, support for scholarship-related problems, and scholarship benefits and college persistence components, namely: academic integration, social integration, support service satisfaction, degree commitment, institutional commitment, and academic conscientiousness. A descriptive-correlational design was utilized with a convenience sampling technique to select 67 DOST scholars as respondents. Self-reported assessments were used to measure the variables. The results show that the students were very satisfied with the scholarship services, and they are highly persistent in all indicators except academic conscientiousness. However, there is no significant relationship between satisfaction with scholarship services and college persistence. Studying other potential variables related to scholarship services and implementing policies to improve college persistence is recommended.

KEYWORDS: satisfaction, scholarship, DOST, college persistence

INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve an advantage and further boost the nation's competitiveness, it is recognized that state universities and colleges' institutional capabilities must be upgraded and that quality higher education must be offered for developing, modifying, and transferring innovations, especially in the field of science and technology (Halili, 2014). In relation to this, students are urged to enroll in courses related to these in-demand disciplines (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2016). However, because of a dearth of resources, not everyone can pursue courses that are related to science and technology (Sithole et al., 2017), since it has been demonstrated that pursuing these fields calls for more student support, including in terms of finances (Rafanan & De Guzman, 2020).

In attempting to improve how the nation provides opportunities for students to have a competitive higher education, an overview of the existing regulatory procedures and control systems regarding assistance in education are key processes to be considered (Halili, 2014). One of the aids provided in tertiary education is a government-funded scholarship. In the Philippines, the one that is directly aligned with science and technology is being offered by the Department of Science and Technology - Science Education Institute (DOST-SEI) through its undergraduate scholarship program. This form of government assistance is given emphasis, especially in response to the declining number of graduates of STEM programs in the country (Anito & Morales, 2019).

The S&T Undergraduate Scholarships Program seeks to encourage and persuade gifted Filipino students to undertake lifelong professions in science and technology while also ensuring a stable, sufficient supply of skilled S&T human resources that can propel the country into development. The scholarships they offer include the DOST-SEI Merit Scholarship Program, Republic Act No. 7687, and the JLSS (DOST, n.d.). Each type of program has its own corresponding qualifications, privileges, and responsibilities.

In this regard, the department maintains a connection with its scholars through the different services it offers. This has its underpinnings in the widely recognized global necessity to support students' welfare even outside of their main academic needs (Bucad Jr. & Perez, 2021). In essence, it is encouraged that service assessments by the government and other private institutions be embraced and developed to assess the value and quality of the services provided in this country (Mercado Jr. et al., 2015). The satisfaction survey is an information management tool that periodically encapsulates the viewpoint of the students by evaluating the performance of a certain organization. This venture will immediately establish transparent feedback to the relevant agency for the

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

purpose of improvement (Mehdipour & Balaramulu, 2013). This is why the DOST -SEI have assessed the level of satisfaction of undergraduate scholar graduates in 2015 regarding the services they provide. However, it is limited to scholars during that year, and region IV-A scholars are not included as respondents. Mainly, the services include scholarship updates, support for scholars' organizations and activities, scholarship staff assistance, support for scholarship-related problems, and scholarship benefits (DOST, SEI, 2015).

Scholarship updates are about the dissemination of relevant information and announcements from the department. Support to scholar's organization and activities on the other hand, support for scholars' organizations and activities is given through the Science and Technology Learning Assistance Program (STLAP). Included in this are activities that will foster students' intellectual capacities and psycho-social abilities, give them the coping mechanisms they need for college, and instill responsibility to society, leadership, academic achievement, and moral fortitude. Meanwhile, scholarship staff assistance is given by the Undergraduate Science and Technology Scholarship Programs' implementation section, as they are in charge of meeting the needs of the scholars from the particular time, they submitted their scholarship applications until they completed their degrees, among other duties. Support for scholarship-related problems is also extended to the students as the Scholars Associations in the universities and colleges organize events including tutorials, contests, exposure tours, socialization activities, and social immersions to further the academic and personal growth of the scholars. Lastly, scholarship benefits are also given to the scholars, including tuition and other school fees (for scholars enrolled in private HEIs), learning materials and/or connectivity allowance, monthly living allowance, clothing allowance, transportation allowance (for those studying outside of their home province), group accident and health insurance, thesis allowance, and graduation allowance (DOST, n.d.).

These services are manifestations of not just the academic but also the social relations of the students with the organization, which is shown to have an impact on their motivation to continue their college education. This is in fact anchored to the Student Integration Model of Tinto (1993), which states that students who become involved in the social and academic life of an organization are more likely to stay enrolled in their college courses. Students who become incorporated into a college by forming relationships, joining groups, or participating in academic activities are more likely to stay around than those who do not. This gave birth to the notion that students' persistence, in which, during their tertiary education is a key ingredient to the success of their future careers (Lakhal et al., 2020).

College persistence encompasses a student's motivation, ability, and tendency to continue attending college (Shiban, 2013). It reflects students' effective completion of courses and accomplishments, which is one indicator that would determine how to increase achievement and enhance transitions within the educational pathway toward scholastic goals. Increased employment rates, improved workplace conditions, better compensation and benefits, higher savings rates, and greater individual and professional flexibility are just a few of the advantages of developing persistence in college (Andrade et al., 2022). Thus, it is relevant to be explored during this period.

Six reliable factors of college persistence were developed, including academic integration, social integration, satisfaction with support services, degree commitment, institutional commitment, and academic conscientiousness (Davidson et al., 2009). The manner in which students develop as a result of their interactions with the college is reflected in their academic and social integration. In addition, the views that students have about the school depend on how well it satisfies their requirements connected to school outside of the classroom, which lies on support services satisfaction. The amount of attention that students place on obtaining a diploma on the other hand is regarded as degree commitment. Meanwhile, student confidence and satisfaction with their choice of college or university are measured by their institutional commitment. Lastly, in a learning environment, conscientiousness is characterized by high levels of deliberation, sound impulse control, and goal-directed activities.

Since higher education is regarded as one of the best engines for social mobility, continuing education at this level has taken on massive significance both domestically and globally. To pursue this, students applied for financial assistance, which asserts that it is a significant factor in college attendance (Lim & Wang, 2016). This is because students enrolling in higher education institutions can significantly reduce their educational costs with financial aid in the form of subsidies (Avery, 2014). This shows a connection with the scholarship programs that are offered for college students.

Furthermore, there have been studies in different countries that explored the relationship between financial aids and persistence (Santelices et al., 2015; see also Herzog, 2017; and Qayyum et al., 2018). They found varying results in studying the extent of the effect of financial support to students' likelihood to persist in their studies. Most of these studies revolved around student loans and grants that are available in their academic contexts. This strengthens the association of scholarships to students' persistence in college and the need to conduct this line of study in the country.

In the Philippines, satisfaction with scholarship programs is also studied with college persistence (Purigay, 2020). However, it is focused on the financial aid Tertiary Education Subsidy (TES) implemented by the UniFAST Board. No further research has studied the satisfaction of the students in terms of the holistic services offered by a scholarship program, specifically the one from the Department of Science and Technology (DOST). This gap will be addressed in the present study as it seeks to

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

determine the professed satisfaction with DOST scholarship services and its relation to college persistence among students at one state university in Laguna.

Thus, the significance of the variables presented above lead the researchers to conduct the present study. The researchers created the following framework to better understand the variables and purpose of this study.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the relationship between scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence of students at Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus. Scholarship services satisfaction is categorized into five aspects: scholarship updates, support to scholars' organization/ activities, scholarship staff assistance, support to scholarship-related problems, and scholarship benefits. On the other hand, college persistence includes six components which are academic integration, social integration, support services satisfaction, degree commitment, institutional commitment, and academic conscientiousness. A quantitative method will be utilized to collect all necessary data regarding the relationship between scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence. The findings of this study may serve as basis for improving scholarship service delivery, implementation, and management.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1 Sex;
- 1.2 Socioeconomic status;
- 1.3 Year Level;
- 1.4 Field of Study; and
- 1.5 Type of Scholarship?

2. What is the respondents' level of satisfaction towards scholarship services in terms of:

- 2.1 Scholarship updates;
- 2.2 Support to scholars' organization and activities;
- 2.3 Scholarship staff assistance;
- 2.4 Support to scholarship-related problems; and
- 2.5 Scholarship benefits?

3. How do the respondents perceive their college persistence in terms of:

- 3.1 Academic integration;
- 3.2 Social integration;
- 3.3 Support services satisfaction;
- 3.4 Degree commitment;
- 3.5 Institutional commitment; and
- 3.6 Academic conscientiousness?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of satisfaction towards scholarship services and perceived college persistence?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction towards scholarship services and perceived college persistence.

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted at the Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus. A quantitative method was utilized to collect all necessary data regarding the relationship between scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence.

Research Design

A descriptive correlational research design was used to collect all the needed data to be gathered for the study. This was used to identify the correlations between two or more variables in the same population and to describe the relationships between variables (Curtis et al., 2016).

In descriptive correlational research, researchers collected data from a sample of participants, usually through surveys or observations, and then use statistical methods, such as correlation analysis or regression analysis, to analyze the data. This describes and summarizes the characteristics of a population or a phenomenon being studied.

Descriptive research is described as a research approach used to correctly characterize existent occurrences. The researcher must collect accessible all the necessary data using research tools such as tests, questionnaires, interviews, and even observation (Atmowardoyo, 2018). In this study, a self-made questionnaire survey was used as a tool in gathering the student responses about their perception towards scholarship services of the Departments of Science and Technology (DOST) to their college persistence.

Participants

The researcher employed convenience sampling strategy in picking the target group of respondents. This technique lets the researchers reach out to participants that are available during the data gathering procedures of the study (Etikan et al., 2016).

The study sample includes all S&T Undergraduate Scholarship and Junior Level Science Scholarship recipients at Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus. The self-made questionnaire survey was sent to respondents and administered in the month of February 2023. To ensure that the questionnaires are reliable with the target respondents a qualified statistician ran a reliability test to assess the reliability of using the various questionnaires.

Instrumentation

The researcher will use three main data gathering instruments:

Part 1: This is a self-made questionnaire on the profile of respondents in terms of sex, socioeconomic status, year level, field of study, and type of scholarship.

Part 2: A self-made questionnaire was administered to measure the level of satisfaction of respondents regarding scholarship services in terms of scholarship updates, support to scholars' organization/ activities, scholarship staff assistance, support to scholarship-related problems, and scholarship benefits. This will be a four-point Likert scale with the following scale descriptors: 4 – very satisfied, 3 – satisfied, 2 – dissatisfied, and 1 – very dissatisfied. This was validated by experts to ensure the instrument's validity and reliability.

Part 3: It was an adapted questionnaire from Davidson et al. (2009) which measures the college persistence of the respondents in terms of six aspects namely: academic integration, social integration, support services satisfaction, degree commitment, institutional commitment, and academic conscientiousness. This is a four-point Likert scale with the following scale descriptors: 4 – Strongly agree, 3 – Agree, 2 – Disagree, and 1 – Strongly disagree.

Data Gathering Procedure

Ethical Consideration

The researcher maintained complete confidentiality when dealing with test results and respondents' personal data. Only the researchers and thesis adviser have access to the data collection's findings. Data was solely used for the analysis; no other self-serving purposes will be undertaken. The identities of the respondents will not be disclosed in this publication.

For this research, the questionnaire was divided into three parts: respondents' profile, level of satisfaction regarding scholarship services, and measure of college persistence. The self-made questionnaire was administered through google forms for an easier gathering of data and responses. After various checking and validation of the instruments, it was forwarded to the respondents via messenger. The gathering and analysis of data was run in the month of February 2023.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the implementation was analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Frequency Distribution and Percentage: This tool was used to show the frequency of a specified information in a data set. A corresponding percentage was computed to describe how the data is relative to the sample (Kaur et al., 2018). In this study, the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, socioeconomic status, year level, field of study, and type of scholarship, was analyzed through this tool.

Weighted mean and ranking. These descriptive statistics analyzed the average of each data set. This shows how the ratings of the respondents' cluster around the center of the distribution (Kaur et al., 2018). This was utilized for the data that was gathered from

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

the survey questionnaires of scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence. The means of each indicator showed which one received the highest rank.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to analyze the relationship between scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence.

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) shows the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables (Tan, 2014). This coefficient is a number between -1 and 1. A positive r shows that there is a direct relationship between scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence. On the other hand, a negative r describes an inverse relationship, that is, when one variable changes, the other variable also changes, but in the opposite direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the gathered data, statistical analyses, and interpretations. Figures and tables were utilized to systematically present the findings of this study. The conclusions and recommendations of the study were based on the collected data and its respective interpretations that focused on the satisfaction on scholarship services and college persistence of the respondents.

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	42	62.7
Female	25	37.3
Total	67	100

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents' sex in terms of male and female. The data collected includes 42 males and 25 females selected from the population of DOST scholars inside the university.

Table 2: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Socioeconomic Status

Level	Frequency	Percent
Low	42	62.7
Middle	25	37.3
High	0	0
Total	67	100

The distribution of the respondents' level of socioeconomic status namely low, middle, and high is presented in Table 2. It can be observed that most of the respondents chose the low socioeconomic status which coincides with the set qualifications of DOST scholarship (DOST, n.d.). Out of the research sample, 42 students perceive that they fall under the low level, 25 students were in the middle level, and none of them perceive their socioeconomic status in the high level.

Table 3: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Level	Frequency	Percent
First	14	20.9
Second	11	16.4
Third	20	29.9
Fourth	22	32.8
Total	67	100

Meanwhile, Table 3 indicates the distribution of the respondents in terms of their current year level in their tertiary education in the university. Fourteen of them are first-year students, 11 are second-year, 20 are third-years, and 22 are fourth-years.

Table 4: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Field of Study

Field	Frequency	Percent
Arts and Sciences	20	29.85
Computer Studies	5	7.46
Engineering	34	50.74
Teacher Education	8	11.95
Total	67	100

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

Table 4 illustrates how the respondents differ in terms of their fields of study. It can be seen that half of the participants (34) were studying engineering courses, one third of them are from arts and sciences, only a few of them are under computer studies (5) and teacher education (8).

Table 5: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Type of Scholarship

Type of Scholarship	Frequency	Percent
RA 7687	48	62.7
Merit	4	37.3
JLSS under RA 10612	5	7.5
JLSS under RA 7687	9	13.4
JLSS under MERIT	1	1.5
Total	67	100

The participants also vary in terms of the types of scholarship that they have, which are described in Table 5. Most of the respondents fall under RA 7687 scholarship with 48 students. A few of them fall under the other types of scholarships namely: Merit (4), JLSS under RA 10612 (5), JLSS under RA 7687 (9), and JLSS under Merit (1).

Table 6 shows the satisfaction of the students in terms of scholarship updates. The results posit that the respondents are all very satisfied, with an overall mean of 3.43. They have the highest satisfaction in terms of the quality of information they receive regarding any scholarship concerns, with a mean of 3.45, interpreted as very satisfied. Meanwhile, the next indicators that received the same mean of 3.42 include the frequency and timeliness of updates they receive about their scholarship. This also implies that the students are very satisfied. This means that the organization is able to provide efficient service in terms of student affairs. This is an essential duty that the students may perceive as highly useful as they will be informed about the features and activities involving them (Caulilan & Tattao, 2022).

Table 6: Satisfaction towards scholarship services in terms of scholarship Updates

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I felt ____ with the quality of information (detailed, complete, and concise) I receive from the official Facebook group in terms of any announcement or concern regarding my scholarship.	3.45	.634	Very Satisfied
I felt ____ with the frequency of updates I receive from the official group chat whenever there is relevant information about my scholarship	3.42	.721	Very Satisfied
I felt ____ with the timeliness of updates I receive from the school coordinator regarding any concern about my scholarship.	3.42	.655	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.43	.670	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Very Dissatisfied), 1.76-2.50 (Dissatisfied), 2.51-3.25 (Satisfied), 3.26-4.0 (Very Satisfied)

Table 7 presents the satisfaction of the students in terms of the support they receive regarding the activities that the organization provides for them. It can be gleaned that the students are all very satisfied with this service, as it has an overall mean of 3.49. The indicator with the highest mean of 3.54 suggests that the respondents are very satisfied with the programs that were initiated to develop their knowledge. The next indicator with a mean of 3.48 involves the activities that build the scholars rapport, with which they are also very satisfied. This is also true for the last indicator, which received a mean of 3.45. It is about the provided seminars and trainings that develop the skills of the respondents, with which they are very satisfied.

Table 7: Satisfaction towards scholarship services in terms of support to scholars' organization/ activities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I felt ____ with the programs implemented by the DOST (regional or school-based) to strengthen my knowledge in my field.	3.54	.559	Very Satisfied
I felt ____ with the seminars and trainings that the DOST (regional or school-based) provide in order to develop my skills in my field.	3.45	.634	Very Satisfied
I felt ____ with the activities that the DOST (regional or school-based) initiates to build camaraderie with my co-scholars.	3.48	.587	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.49	.594	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Very Dissatisfied), 1.76-2.50 (Dissatisfied), 2.51-3.25 (Satisfied), 3.26-4.0 (Very Satisfied)

This is one of the commendable features of the services offered by the DOST since they are inclined toward the holistic goals of the education process: to develop not just the cognitive but also the psychomotor and social skills of the students. This may explain why

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

the students are very satisfied with this particular service, as they may feel that they are more engaged in the organization to which they belong (Zhu et al., 2021).

Table 8 presents the scholar's satisfaction in terms of the assistance they receive from the DOST staff. With an overall mean of 3.51, this suggests that the students are very satisfied with this service. The highest mean of 3.58 deals with the approachability of the staff whenever the students meet them for any scholarship concerns. The next indicator received a mean of 3.54, which is about the usefulness of the help given by the staff, and lastly, the timeliness of their response received the lowest mean of 3.40. Despite the varied means, the students are very satisfied with all the indicators mentioned. The result is a good manifestation of the ideals of a student in terms of institutional services. It helps to retain students in the organization, which is only possible if all of the services that support academic needs are of high caliber (Kanwar & Sanjeeva, 2022).

Table 8: Satisfaction towards scholarship services in terms of scholarship staff assistance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I felt ___ with the approachability of the Regional DOST staff or school-based DOST coordinators whenever I meet them for any scholarship concern.	3.58	.581	Very Satisfied
I felt ___ with the timeliness of the response of the Regional DOST staff or school-based DOST coordinators whenever I send them an email or message concerning my scholarship.	3.40	.698	Very Satisfied
I felt ___ with the usefulness of the assistance given by the Regional DOST staff or school-based DOST coordinators whenever I have a concern about my scholarship.	3.54	.611	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.51	.630	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Very Dissatisfied), 1.76-2.50 (Dissatisfied), 2.51-3.25 (Satisfied), 3.26-4.0 (Very Satisfied)

Table 9 presents the satisfaction of the respondents with the support they receive from any scholarship-related problem, which garnered an overall mean of 3.45. Two indicators received the highest mean of 3.48. It includes the assistance given by the staff regarding a concern about requirements and the problems they encounter regarding their financial assistance, with which the scholars are very satisfied. Meanwhile, the indicator with the lowest mean of 3.42 and a very satisfied interpretation is about the solution that the staff suggests for other scholarship-related problems.

Table 9: Satisfaction towards scholarship services in terms of support to scholarship-related problems

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I felt ___ with the assistance given to me by the coordinators (regional/school-based) whenever I have a problem regarding my requirements.	3.48	.560	Very Satisfied
I felt ___ with the response I receive from the DOST coordinator (regional/school-based) whenever I have a problem regarding my stipend.	3.48	.562	Very Satisfied
I felt ___ with the solution that the DOST coordinator (regional/school-based) suggests whenever I have a problem regarding my scholarship.	3.42	.609	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.45	.577	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Very Dissatisfied), 1.76-2.50 (Dissatisfied), 2.51-3.25 (Satisfied), 3.26-4.0 (Very Satisfied)

Considering the idea that problems regarding scholarship are in need of suitable and immediate solutions, the result may suggest that the services offered by the DOST staff are good enough for scholars to remain committed to their academic and organizational duties despite the problems they experience (Abdul-Rahaman et al., 2018).

Table 10: Satisfaction towards scholarship services in terms of scholarship benefits

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I felt ___ with the benefits I received from the DOST.	3.90	.308	Very Satisfied
I felt ___ with the amount of financial assistance I receive from DOST.	3.75	.586	Very Satisfied
I felt ___ with the timeliness of the release of DOST financial assistance.	3.07	.858	Satisfied
I felt ___ with the usefulness of every DOST benefit in my undergraduate studies	3.85	.359	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.64	.528	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Very Dissatisfied), 1.76-2.50 (Dissatisfied), 2.51-3.25 (Satisfied), 3.26-4.0 (Very Satisfied)

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

Table 10 presents the satisfaction of the scholars with the scholarship benefits they receive. It has an overall mean of 3.64, which indicates that the students are very satisfied with this service. The indicator with the highest mean of 3.90 means that the scholars are very satisfied with the benefits they receive from the DOST. They are also very satisfied with the usefulness of the scholarship during their undergraduate studies, as it garnered a mean score of 3.85. Same goes with the amount of financial aid the students receive, with which they are also very satisfied, as it got a mean of 3.75. On the other hand, the lowest indicator, with a mean of 3.07, suggests that the students are satisfied with the timeliness of the release of their financial assistance.

This result may indicate that the students have had useful advantages in terms of their scholarship benefits. This may also have a favorable impact on their experiences as students, as they may be more determined to pursue their fields, especially if they are provided with a substantial support system in terms of their academic needs (Moneva & Jumag, 2020).

Table 11: College Persistence in terms of Academic Integration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I understand the thinking of my instructors when they lecture or ask students to answer questions in class.	3.49	.504	Highly Integrated
I am satisfied with the extent of my intellectual growth and interest in ideas since coming here.	3.40	.552	Highly Integrated
I am satisfied with the quality of instruction I am receiving here.	3.49	.612	Highly Integrated
I feel the concern that the faculty here shows on my intellectual growth.	3.43	.583	Highly Integrated
I am interested in the things that are being said during class discussions.	3.55	.501	Highly Integrated
I see a connection between what I am learning here and my future career possibilities.	3.60	.494	Highly Integrated
I believe that my instructors impose reasonable requirements on students.	3.42	.607	Highly Integrated
I am satisfied with the amount of interaction that I have with the faculty.	3.57	.529	Highly Integrated
Overall	3.49	.548	Highly Integrated

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Integrated at All), 1.76-2.50 (Lowly Integrated), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Integrated), 3.26-4.0 (Highly Integrated)

Table 11 shows the college persistence in terms of academic integration. It can be seen that the eight indicators are all highly integrated. Their satisfaction with the amount of interaction with the faculty got the highest mean of 3.57 or highly integrated while on the other hand, their satisfaction with their intellectual growth and interest in ideas from then got the lowest mean of 3.40 but still classified as highly integrated. This shows that student's commitment to the college and academic aspirations are influenced by their social and academic integration into the college community, which in turn affects their decision to stay enrolled and move closer to completion (Ganem & Manasse, 2021).

Table 12: College Persistence in terms of Social Integration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I have interpersonal relationships with other students which had an impact on my personal growth, attitudes, and values.	3.54	.532	Highly Integrated
I have interpersonal relationships with other students which had an impact on my intellectual growth and interest in ideas.	3.52	.587	Highly Integrated
I have a strong sense of connectedness with others faculty, students, and staff on this campus.	3.25	.704	Moderately Integrated
I have a lot in common with the other students here.	3.33	.637	Highly Integrated
I am satisfied with my overall social life here including friendships, college organizations, and extracurricular activities.	3.48	.587	Highly Integrated
I have my closest friends here with me in college.	3.48	.636	Highly Integrated
I enjoy being with other students here.	3.52	.560	Highly Integrated
I wear my college uniform with the university's emblems.	3.58	.527	Highly Integrated
Overall	3.46	.596	Highly Integrated

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Integrated at All), 1.76-2.50 (Lowly Integrated), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Integrated), 3.26-4.0 (Highly Integrated)

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

In Table 12, college persistence in terms of social integration was presented using the eight indicators. The indicator that got the highest mean is the students wearing their college uniforms with the university emblems which has a mean of 3.58 that falls under highly integrated. In terms of having a strong sense of connectedness with other faculty, students, and staff on this campus the results showed that it got the lowest mean from all the indicators which has a mean of 3.25 which is under moderately integrated. Overall, it can be seen from the data result that most of the indicators still fall under highly integrated. This shows that institutions and their people are essential for students' personality development. Wherein institutions provide students with social integration and nurturing mental health they need to alter their personalities as needed to prepare them to act as responsible individuals (Shasheen et. al, 2020).

Using the six factors in the table, Table 13 displays the college persistence in terms of supportive services satisfaction. The findings indicate that the respondents are very satisfied with the assistance given to DOST scholars. The greatest mean was obtained for course offers, rules and regulations, and registration processes (3.48), indicating a high level of satisfaction. The other 5 indicators also listed under "very satisfied" which according to the study of Arif et al. (2016), university management's that offers support services enables students' attitudes to proper reinforcement, career development, and effective engagement in teaching and learning.

Table 13: College Persistence in terms of Supportive Services Satisfaction

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I am satisfied with the academic advisement I receive here.	3.42	.555	Very Satisfied
I am satisfied with the way the institution communicates academic rules, course requirements, campus news and events, extracurricular activities, and financial aid and scholarship opportunities to students.	3.42	.555	Very Satisfied
I can easily get answers to my questions about things related to your education here.	3.33	.561	Very Satisfied
I am satisfied with the amount of input I can have on matters such as course offerings, rules and regulations, and registration procedures.	3.48	.503	Very Satisfied
I am satisfied with the way the university meets my needs which are different from the majority of students here.	3.39	.576	Very Satisfied
I feel that students are handled fairly in here.	3.40	.524	Very Satisfied
Overall	3.41	.546	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Very Dissatisfied), 1.76-2.50 (Dissatisfied), 2.51-3.25 (Satisfied), 3.26-4.0 (Very Satisfied)

The five indicators in Table 14 make it evident that all of the respondents' mean college persistence rates fit within the category of extremely dedicated in terms of degree commitment. The third and fourth indicators, which demonstrate students' great dedication to obtaining a college degree and their strong determination to pursue that degree, received the highest means. Braxton et al. (2014) made reference that a college degree may be obtained by a student's perseverance and dedication to action, particularly in regard to academic objectives and specific goal behavior.

Table 14: College Persistence in terms of Degree Commitment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I have friends and family who would be disappointed if I quit school.	3.67	.533	Highly Committed
At this moment in time, I am certain that I will earn a college degree.	3.63	.517	Highly Committed
At this moment in time, I have strong commitment to earn a college degree, here or elsewhere.	3.75	.438	Highly Committed
I have a strong intention to persist in my pursuit of the degree, here or elsewhere.	3.76	.430	Highly Committed
I have a supportive family in my pursuit of a college degree, in terms of their encouragement and expectations.	3.64	.483	Highly Committed
Overall	3.69	.394	Highly Committed

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Committed at All), 1.76-2.50 (Lowly Committed), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Committed), 3.26-4.0 (Highly Committed)

It can be gleaned from Table 15 that college students are highly committed in terms of the institution that they belong into. This can be shown in the overall mean of 3.28. This means that they are persistent to continue and finish their studies in their current

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

university. With a mean of 3.72, they are highly committed the most to earning their degrees in their school. Dustan (2018) mentioned that the choice of a collegiate institution is a high-stakes decision where schools are expected to have an impact on later-outcomes like the rate of graduation. Meanwhile, it can be seen that a clear discrepancy of the mean of the last indicator with a 2.45. This could mean that students are not giving it enough thought to transfer schools because they plan on staying on their college until graduation. This was explained by Tobolowsky and Bers (2018) wherein they stated that

Table 15: College Persistence in terms of Institutional Commitment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I am likely to earn a degree from here.	3.72	.454	Highly Committed
I am confident that this is the right university for me.	3.57	.529	Highly Committed
I am likely to reenroll here next semester.	3.40	.836	Highly Committed
I have given enough thought to stopping my education here perhaps transferring to another college, going to work, or leaving for other reasons.	2.45	1.17	Lowly Committed
Overall	3.28	.748	Highly Committed

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Committed at All), 1.76-2.50 (Lowly Committed), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Committed), 3.26-4.0 (Highly Committed)

college school decisions are rather spontaneous than planned. Incoming tertiary students can be described with this type decision-making skills which could be associated with their level of thinking regarding transferring schools.

Table 16: College Persistence in terms of Academic Conscientiousness

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I miss class for reasons other than illness or participation in school-sponsored activities.	2.09	.965	Lowly Conscientious
I turn in assignments past the due date.	2.10	.956	Lowly Conscientious
I am disinterested in academic work and do as little as possible.	2.00	.985	Lowly Conscientious
Overall	2.06	.968	Lowly Conscientious

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Conscientious at All), 1.76-2.50 (Lowly Conscientious), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Conscientious), 3.26-4.0 (Highly Conscientious)

Lastly, Table 16 indicates the college persistence of respondents in terms of their academic conscientiousness. It was revealed that they are lowly conscientious, in general, with an average of 2.06. This means that students could be described with low level of concern over completing their school works. This behavior is observed with students under blended learning conditions like the current situation of the research locale (Theobald et al., 2018). Less conscientious students are likely to neglect their academic duties due to the increased self-regulatory demands of blended learning.

Table 17: Test of Correlation between Scholarship Services Satisfaction and College Persistence

Correlations	Academic Integration	Social Integration	Supportive Services Satisfaction	Degree Commitment	Institutional Commitment	Academic Conscientiousness
Scholarship Updates	.150	.163	.163	.104	.060	.018
Support to scholars' organization and activities	.203	.184	.176	.192	-.019	-.117
Scholarship staff assistance	.136	.186	.118	.126	.051	-.023
Support to scholarship-related problems	.167	.186	.159	.021	-.011	-.078
Scholarship benefits	.107	.065	.056	.032	.005	-.043

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Professed Student Satisfaction on Scholarship Services and its Relation to College Persistence in One State University in Laguna

The table above shows the test of correlation between the indicators of scholarship services satisfaction and college persistence. It can be observed that there is no significant relationship between the tested indicators. However, most of the variables have weak correlation which means that they could be associated at a certain extent.

In terms of scholarship updates, the highest correlation coefficients were displayed by its association with social integration and supportive services satisfaction. According to Raaper et al. (2022), establishing a good student support system creates a social network during the pandemic. In this case, scholarship updates provide scholars opportunities to interact with fellow scholars within their organization. These student experiences may also give wellbeing support for students who were under the new normal of education. Moreover, Cidral et al. (2018) assert that one of the determinants of e-learning success is a successful information system. They found out that students under online education will be more satisfied with their learning when useful information are disseminated properly. Similarly, being updated with new information regarding scholarship may also influence the students' satisfaction with school services in their university.

Supporting scholar's organization and its activities obtained the highest correlation with academic integration. This may indicate that satisfaction on organizational concerns may be related with how students connect themselves to academic-related activities (Buckley & Lee, 2021). Also, being involved in clubs and other events outside the classroom improve overall student experience in their college education. This can be explained by the positive, indirect effect of extracurricular activities to academic performance of students (Seow & Pan, 2014). They discussed that club activities let students practice and develop competencies that improve academic achievement including efficient time management, collaboration, and personal organization.

Dwyer (2015) states that student-faculty interactions are essential parts of students' social integration in school. This may support the association of scholarship staff assistance and support to scholarship-related problems with social integration. Asking for help regarding scholarships from assigned personnel gives way for new ways of socialization for DOST scholars. Being integrated socially should not be limited to their peers but may also go beyond their social circle.

Lastly, scholarship benefits satisfaction revealed that among the persistence indicators, it is associated with academic integration the most. This can be explained by the gains that scholarship aids provide to enrollment and student success (Ganem & Manasse, 2011). Moreover, high test-scorers were found to more likely persist in their college education with the help of their scholarship benefits. Also, the small negative correlations of some of the variables with academic consciousness may be influenced by the impact of COVID-19 to students' wellbeing which influenced their concern regarding their academic duties and responsibilities (Plakhotnik et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of this study suggests that the scholars are very satisfied with all the services provided by the DOST. This implies that they are delighted with the services that the DOST offers in terms of scholarship updates, support for scholars' organizations and activities, scholarship staff assistance, support for scholarship-related problems, and scholarship benefits. Meanwhile, their college persistence varied in some ways. According to the result, they are highly integrated in terms of academic and social aspects. They are also very satisfied with the supportive services being offered to them. They are highly committed to their degrees as well as the institution, but they are lowly conscientious in terms of academic aspects. It is also evident that scholarship services and college persistence do not significantly relate to one another. However, the majority of the variables exhibit weak correlations.

The associations between scholarship upgrades, social integration, and satisfaction with supportive services exhibited the strongest correlation. Supporting student organizations and their activities also showed the strongest association with academic integration. Assistance from scholarship officials and support for issues with social integration associated with scholarships are also relevant. Finally, satisfaction with scholarship benefits showed that, among the persistence factors, it is most closely related to academic integration.

Studying the specific components of the two variables that have shown correlation in this research is hereby suggested to determine the underlying factors that may be associated with both of them.

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